

2-TOM, 3-SON

THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN HUMAN DEVELOPMENT IN THE WORLD
COMMUNITY

Allayarova Naila Yakshonor qizi
Tashkent State Technical University Senior teacher
Student: Abdullaeva Kamola Zafarovna

Abstract: the article is devoted to the convention that clearly defines the problems related to achieving practical equality of women and men, i.e. ensuring gender equality, women's practical use of their rights

Key words: gender studies, gender equality, women's rights, legal norms, stereotype, women's entrepreneurship, women's rights, UN, Office of the UN High Commissioner for Human Rights, representative authority, International Organization for Migration

Today, the world community is trying to create international mechanisms with a proper understanding of the role of women in human development. The adoption of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women's Rights by the UN General Assembly on December 18, 1979 is proof of our opinion. This convention is the main document that clearly defines the problems related to achieving practical equality of women and men, that is, ensuring gender equality, women's practical use of their rights. The problems identified in the Convention are multifaceted. In addition to clarifying the relevance of the problems of ending discrimination in various forms, it also reflects the important provisions related to raising the status of women as equal human beings, their political, socio-economic and cultural rights, equal rights with men, and motherhood. Fulfillment of international obligations requires improvement of laws and regulatory legal documents at all levels, accurate monitoring of their implementation, and control over the implementation of international legal acts. By harmonizing international legal documents on ensuring gender equality with national legislation, strong legal foundations are being created in the field of education in our country.

Women's rights and freedoms equal to men's, state policies related to motherhood and childhood, strengthening of women's position in social life, increasing their political

2-TOM, 3-SON

activity, expanding their participation in state and community management deserve special attention.

An effective institutional framework for the protection of women's rights is representative power.

The task of deputies of all levels of representative power is to connect economic growth with human development, to ensure their coherence. It is not for nothing that the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan has emphasized from the international platform that the membership of women in the parliament has doubled in the following years.

Today, the institutional framework for gender equality is expanding in our country. Meanwhile, within the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a new Women's and Gender Equality Committee was established, which is engaged in harmonizing international standards in the national legislation on ensuring women's rights and eliminating any form of discrimination.

As a matter of fact, 49% of our country is made up of women, and almost 64% of them are women under 30 years of age. A number of practical works in the areas of ensuring gender equality and improving the social living conditions of women in our country, comprehensive support and development of the family institution, implementation of universally recognized international norms on eliminating all forms of discrimination of women's rights into national legislation, as well as increasing women's legal culture was carried out.

If we look at how attention is paid to gender issues in the international framework, it can be seen that there are still a number of problems in ensuring gender equality in the world. For example, according to the International Labor Organization, there are 6 working women for every 10 working men. In the 74th session of the UN General Assembly, which began its work on September 24, 2019, the women's wing of the organization did not for nothing highlight the issues of gender equality and the provision of appropriate rights and freedoms for women in order to achieve sustainable development of countries. The fact that only 17

2-TOM, 3-SON

of the 192 speakers during the session of the General Assembly were women was also criticized. Uzbekistan is conscientiously trying to fulfill its international obligations regarding women's issues. Our country, as a member of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination of Women's Rights, pays special attention to the harmonization of its norms with the national legislation. In particular, important steps have been taken in this regard in our country. In September 2019, the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men" and "On protection of women from oppression and violence" were adopted.

The law "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men" emphasizes the prohibition of direct and indirect discrimination of women based on gender. This law was developed in accordance with the decision of the head of our country on March 7, 2019 "On measures to further strengthen guarantees of women's labor rights and support entrepreneurship". The purpose of this law is to protect women from all forms of harassment and violence in marriage, workplace, educational institutions and other places. One of the important goals of the law is to regulate relations in this field, as well as to ensure legal and social protection of victims of harassment and violence.

The Law on Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence lays the groundwork for protecting women by providing assistance to victims of domestic violence, providing them with shelters, hotlines, and mandatory prosecution for not only physical violence, but also psychological or economic crimes. Such measures have been recommended for a long time, in particular by UN human rights agencies.

In 2019 alone, 197 centers for the rehabilitation and adaptation of victims of the use of violence were established. In addition, in order to further strengthen the guarantees and support of labor rights, to help victims of domestic violence, the activities of the Republican Center for Rehabilitation and Adaptation of Victims of Violence and Suicide Prevention and the Center for Women and Girls Entrepreneurship were launched.

2-TOM, 3-SON

The initial payment for housing of 1454 women living in difficult living conditions was paid from the Public Fund for Women and Family Support, and 25 billion was allocated for these purposes. 194 mln. Soum funds were directed. More than 13,000 women in this category were also employed. More than 2,000 female students have shown their effectiveness in the social protection mechanisms. According to the employment program, more than 250 thousand women, including students, were employed. A reserve of more than 6,000 women with political and legal knowledge, innovative ideas and organizational skills was formed.

To sum up, the achievement of gender equality in our country is the key to strengthening the position of women in society, thereby strengthening the family, bringing up a young generation with a high intellectual level, and ensuring the stability of society.

Thus, the educational process organized on the basis of gender differences and equality makes an important contribution to the development of society. In turn, the UN team in Uzbekistan is currently working on gender equality within the framework of the "Sustainable Development Cooperation Program for 2021-2025", which is currently being consulted with all national partners and other stakeholders. will continue to provide comprehensive assistance to the country, and this will certainly be reflected in the field of education.

List of used literature

1. Mirziyoev Sh.M. We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people. - T.: "Uzbekistan", 2017. - 488 p.
2. Mirziyoev Sh.M. We will resolutely continue our path of national development and raise it to a new level. Volume 1. - T.: "Uzbekistan", 2017. - 592 p.
3. Mirziyoev Sh.M. From national revival to national rise. Volume 4. - T.: "Uzbekistan", 2020. - 400 p.

2-TOM, 3-SON

4. Gulabad Qudratullah's daughter, R. Ishmuhamedov, M. Normuhammedova. Traditional and non-traditional education. - Samarkand: "Imam Bukhari International Research Center" publishing house, 2019. 312 p.

5. Ejak E.V. Psikhologicheskoe obespechenie professionalnogo razvitiya pedagoga v usloviyakh riskov sovremennogo obrazovaniya. diss... doc.psychol. science – Rostov-on-Don.: 2017. - 315 p.

6. Xamrayeva Nilufar. (2024). SOCIOLINGUISTIC COMPETENCE AND SOCIOCULTURAL ASPECT OF LANGUAGE. Innovations in Technology and Science Education, 2(17), 466–471. Retrieved from <https://humoscience.com/index.php/itse/article/view/2368>

7. Xamrayeva, N. ., & Olimova , M. . (2023). SOTSIOLINGVISTIKA VA DIALEKTOLOGIYA. Theoretical Aspects in the Formation of Pedagogical Sciences, 2(6), 149–154. извлечено от <http://www.econferences.ru/index.php/tafps/article/view/4872>

8. Xamrayeva, N. ., & Olimova , M. . (2023). SOTSIOLINGVISTIKA VA DIALEKTOLOGIYA. Theoretical Aspects in the Formation of Pedagogical Sciences, 2(6), 149–154. извлечено от <http://www.econferences.ru/index.php/tafps/article/view/4872>

